

Reading Comprehension of Grade 10 Students using Scholastic Literacy Pro: A Short-Term Longitudinal Study

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Abstract

This study examined the reading comprehension performance of Grade 10 students at St. Paul University Surigao during the School Year 2025-2026 using a short-term longitudinal prospective approach. It aimed to determine students' reading comprehension levels through pretest and posttest Lexile scores, identify significant differences when grouped according to sex, class section, and socio-economic status, analyze changes over time, and explore the challenges, strategies, and contextual factors influencing reading development, as well as the perceived effectiveness of the Scholastic Literacy Pro program.

The study employed an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design grounded in the pragmatic paradigm. Quantitative data were collected from 191 Grade 10 students using Scholastic Literacy Pro Lexile assessments, while qualitative data were gathered through semi-structured interviews with five students, one English teacher, and five parents. Quantitative data were analyzed using Frequency and Percentage Distribution, Mann-Whitney U Test, Kruskal-Wallis Test, and Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks Test, while qualitative data were analyzed using NVivo to identify emerging themes.

Findings revealed that most students were initially at the Below Basic level; however, posttest results showed improvement, with increased representation in the Basic and Advanced levels. No significant differences were found based on sex and socio-economic status, while class section showed significant differences, with Science class students performing better. Significant improvement over time was observed. Qualitative findings highlighted vocabulary limitations, low motivation, and digital distractions as key challenges, while guided instruction, parental support, and structured routines were effective strategies. The study concludes that reading comprehension development is a gradual, multifaceted process influenced by instructional practices and contextual factors.

Keywords: *Reading Comprehension, Scholastic Literacy Pro, Lexile Scores, Reading Interventions, Short-term Longitudinal Study.*

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Introduction

Reading is a fundamental skill that forms the basis of education and academic achievement. It is the process of decoding symbols to find meaning, which enables people to learn, grow as critical thinkers, and interact with their surroundings. It also allows people to extend their ideas, access a wealth of information, and improve their communication skills.

In the Philippine context, reading comprehension continues to be a critical concern. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2023) and Servallos (2023), the Philippines ranked 77th out of 81 countries in the 2022 PISA assessment for reading comprehension, slightly improving from its last-place ranking in 2018. However, while the country showed an overall 6.9% improvement in reading comprehension from 2018 to 2022, low-performing students (LPS) experienced a 4.3% decline in proficiency, whereas the performance of top-performing students (TPS) remained stagnant. Recognizing this issue, Vice President and former Education Secretary Sara Duterte has introduced educational reforms that aim to enhance reading comprehension and critical thinking skills among public school students. These efforts underscore the urgent need for sustained interventions to address literacy challenges and ensure that students develop strong reading proficiency for academic and lifelong success.

In response to these persistent literacy challenges, schools and educational institutions have adopted various reading intervention programs and technology-assisted literacy initiatives to improve students' reading engagement and comprehension skills. One of these is Scholastic Literacy Pro, a blended reading management and instructional platform designed to support both independent and guided reading practices through the integration of technology, assessment, and instruction (Literacy Pro: Empowering Reading Success With Data-Driven Tools & Diverse Ebooks, n.d.). One of its key features is the Scholastic Reading Measure (SRM), an adaptive assessment tool that evaluates students' reading ability through Lexile measures, enabling teachers and learners to monitor reading growth and comprehension development.

The program begins with the LitPro Test, which determines students' Lexile levels and generates a Targeted Reading Range (TRR) to guide learners in selecting texts appropriate to their reading ability. Through this, students gain access to a wide range of leveled books and genres that support both independent and teacher-guided reading. The platform also promotes continuous formative assessment through comprehension quizzes, progress tracking, and reading logs that allow teachers, parents, and students to monitor reading performance and Lexile growth.

At the Basic Education Department of St. Paul University Surigao (SPUS), the institution continuously promotes reading engagement among learners through its partnership with Scholastic Literacy Pro. Despite the continuous implementation of

reading initiatives and literacy support programs at St. Paul University Surigao, concerns regarding students' actual reading comprehension performance still persist, particularly in relation to their measured Lexile levels and overall reading proficiency. As revealed in studies by Gortifacion (2017), Arbis et al. (2025), and Oposa et al. (2025), the students' reading performance at St. Paul University Surigao has consistently shown below-average Lexile levels. Correspondingly, these studies were often limited to static, one-time assessments without evaluating how reading comprehension evolved over time or in response to specific interventions. Moreover, prior research lacked a comprehensive exploration of contextual factors, including instructional strategies, student and teacher interventions, and socio-economic influences. There was also an evident gap in examining the long-term progression of students' reading comprehension using both quantitative (test scores) and qualitative (interviews) data. This indicated a clear need for a short-term longitudinal, mixed-methods study that could analyze how various factors influenced reading comprehension outcomes over an extended period.

This study aimed to examine the reading comprehension levels of Grade 10 students at St. Paul University Surigao during the school year 2025–2026 through a short-term longitudinal prospective design. It sought to analyze students' pretest and posttest Lexile levels and investigate how teacher, student, and parental interventions, as well as socio-economic conditions, impacted their reading progress. Specifically, the study aimed to contribute to ongoing literacy efforts and interventions implemented to increase the reading comprehension level of learners. The researcher collected pretest data from the Scholastic before identifying the implementation of any interventions, conducted interviews with stakeholders to determine practices and challenges related to reading support, and then collected posttest data several months later. The ultimate goal of the study was to determine whether and how these combined factors influenced the improvement of students' reading comprehension over time.

Materials and Methods

This study employed an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design, as described by Creswell and Plano Clark (2018), to comprehensively examine how Grade 10 students' reading comprehension develops over time. This design involves two distinct but connected phases: the initial collection and analysis of quantitative data, followed by qualitative exploration to provide a deeper understanding and context, and a final quantitative assessment to measure change.

The quantitative phase followed a post-positivist stance and focused on measuring changes in students' reading comprehension using pretest and posttest Lexile scores generated by the Scholastic Literacy Pro program. Meanwhile, the qualitative component, situated between the pretest and posttest, explored the contextual and instructional factors that may have influenced student reading development.

The study was conducted at St. Paul University Surigao during the School Year 2025–2026. The quantitative participants consisted of 191 Grade 10 students selected through total population sampling. For the qualitative phase, purposive sampling was used to select five students representing different Lexile performance levels, one Grade 10 English teacher implementing the Scholastic Literacy Pro program, and five parents from different class sections.

Quantitative data were obtained from the Scholastic Literacy Pro Assessment Tool, which generates Lexile scores to measure students' reading comprehension levels and provides standardized reports that monitor students' reading progress and performance (Scholastic Inc., 2025). Pretest and posttest Lexile scores served as the quantitative data. Qualitative data were collected through semi-structured interviews using a researcher-developed interview guide that focused on reading challenges, strategies, program effectiveness, and contextual factors influencing reading comprehension.

Pretest and posttest assessments were administered by the school through the Scholastic Literacy Pro program. The researcher secured permission to access the official Lexile results from the Scholastic program consultant. Qualitative interviews were conducted after the pretest and prior to posttest to provide explanations for the observed statistical findings.

Quantitative data were analyzed using Frequency Count and Percentage Computation, Mann-Whitney U tests, Kruskal-Wallis tests, and Wilcoxon Signed-Rank tests. Qualitative data were analyzed through thematic analysis using NVivo software. Integration of quantitative and qualitative findings was achieved through a joint display approach and interpreted in terms of convergence, expansion, and divergence.

Ethical protocols were observed throughout the study. Necessary permissions were obtained from the institution and relevant authorities. Informed consent was secured from all interview participants, and confidentiality was maintained through the use of coded identifiers and secure data management procedures.

Results

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex, class section, and socio-economic status. In terms of sex, a slightly higher proportion of the respondents were female (52.36%) compared to male students (47.64%). With respect to class section, the majority of the respondents came from the Regular class, comprising 80.10% of the total population, while only 19.90% were from the Science class. In terms of socio-economic status, most of the respondents belonged to the middle-income group (30.89%), followed by those in the upper-middle-income category (25.13%) and lower-middle-income group (21.47%). A smaller proportion of students were classified under high-income (12.57%) and low-income (9.95%) groups.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Profile	f (n=191)	%
Sex		
Male	91	47.64
Female	100	52.36
Class Section		
Science Class	38	19.90
Regular Class	153	80.10
Socio-Economic Status		
Below ₱10,000 (Low Income)	19	9.95
₱10,001 – ₱20,000 (Lower-Middle Income)	41	21.47
₱20,001 – ₱40,000 (Middle Income)	59	30.89
₱40,001 – ₱70,000 (Upper-Middle Income)	48	25.13
Above ₱70,000 (High Income)	24	12.57

Source: Research Data (2025-2026)

Table 2. Pretest and Posttest Comprehension Scores

Levels	f (n=191)	%
Pre-test		
Below Basic	102	53.40
Basic	25	13.09
Proficient	47	24.61
Advanced	17	8.90
Post-test		
Below Basic	92	48.17
Basic	36	18.85
Proficient	39	20.42
Advanced	24	12.57

Source: Scholastic Literacy Pro Lexile Assessment Results

Table 2 presents the distribution of students' reading comprehension levels in the pretest and posttest using the Scholastic Literacy Pro assessment.

The pretest results show that the majority of the students were classified under the Below Basic level (53.40%), followed by those in the Proficient level (24.61%), Basic level (13.09%), and a smaller proportion in the Advanced level (8.90%). In the posttest, the percentage of students in the Below Basic level decreased to 48.17%, while the proportion of those in the Basic level increased to 18.85% and those in the Advanced level increased to 12.57%.

Table 3. Reading Comprehension Performance of Students according to Sex

Profile	Test	U	Z	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Sex	Pre-test	4536.00	-0.04	0.968	Accept H_{01}	Not significant
	Post-test	4399.50	-0.42	0.673	Accept H_{01}	Not significant

Source: Research Data (2025-2026)

Table 3 presents the difference in reading comprehension performance of Grade 10 students when grouped according to sex using the Mann–Whitney U test.

It shows that there is no significant difference in reading comprehension performance between male and female Grade 10 students, both in the pretest and posttest. For the pretest, $U = 4536.00$, $z = -0.04$, $p = 0.968$; for the posttest, $U = 4399.50$, $z = -0.42$, $p = 0.673$ —both p values are much greater than 0.05, so the null hypotheses are retained and the difference by sex is interpreted as not statistically significant. This implies that, in this study, students' reading comprehension performance (as measured by the test scores) does not meaningfully vary by sex at either time point.

Table 4. Reading Comprehension Performance of Students According to Class Section

Profile	Test	U	Z	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Class Section	Pre-test	1804.50	-3.97	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
	Post-test	2056.00	-2.99	0.003	Reject H_{01}	Significant

Source: Research Data (2025-2026)

Table 4 presents the difference in reading comprehension performance of Grade 10 students when grouped according to class section using the Mann–Whitney U test.

The results reveal a significant difference in reading comprehension performance between students in the Science and Regular classes in both the pretest and posttest. In the pretest, students in the two class sections already differed significantly ($U = 1804.50$, $z = -3.97$, $p = 0.000$), indicating that their baseline reading comprehension levels were not the same. This significant difference remained evident in the posttest ($U = 2056.00$, $z = -2.99$, $p = 0.003$), suggesting that disparities between the two groups persisted even after the implementation of reading interventions.

Table 5. Reading Comprehension Performance of Students According to Socio-Economic Status

Profile	Test	Chi-square	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Socio-Economic Status	Pre-test	9.34	0.053	Accept H_{01}	Not significant
	Post-test	6.57	0.160	Accept H_{01}	Not significant

Source: Research Data (2025-2026)

Table 5 presents the difference in reading comprehension performance of Grade 10 students when grouped according to socio-economic status using the Kruskal–Wallis test.

It shows that there is no significant difference in reading comprehension performance among Grade 10 students when grouped by socio-economic status, for both the pretest and posttest. For the pretest, $H = 9.34$, $p = 0.053$, and for the posttest, $H = 6.57$, $p = 0.160$ —both p values are greater than 0.05, so the null hypotheses are retained and the differences across SES groups are interpreted as not statistically significant. This suggests that, in this study, socio economic status does not appear to have a meaningful effect on students’ reading comprehension performance at either time point.

Table 6. Reading Comprehension Performance Over time

	Post-test –Pre-test
Z	-3.61 ^b
p-value	0.000
Decision	Reject H_{02}
Interpretation	Significant

Source: Scholastic Literacy Pro Lexile Assessment Results

Table 6 presents the difference in reading comprehension performance of students between the pretest and posttest using the Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks test. It shows that there is a significant difference in reading comprehension performance over time, indicating that students’ scores improved (or changed) between pretest and posttest. The result, $z = -3.61$, $p = 0.000$, is well below the 0.05 threshold, so the null hypothesis (no difference over time) is rejected.

Table 7. Themes on Challenges in Reading Comprehension

Theme	Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gadget and social media distraction	Students diverted attention to phones and apps instead of reading	9	82%
Difficulty with vocabulary and complex texts	Struggles in understanding unfamiliar words and deeper meanings	7	64%
Academic workload and fatigue	Heavy school tasks reduced time and energy for reading	6	55%
Lack of focus in school environment	Noise and distractions in classroom affected comprehension	5	45%
Low motivation and reliance on summaries	Students avoided full reading and depended on shortcuts	5	45%

Source: Interview Data

Table 7 presents the major challenges encountered by Grade 10 students in understanding texts and improving reading comprehension, based on the qualitative coding of interview data. The most frequently reported challenge was gadget and social media distraction (82%).

Table 8. Themes on Strategies and Interventions

Theme	Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Teacher-led instructional strategies	Guided reading, vocabulary tasks, and comprehension activities	10	91%
Reward and incentive systems	Coupons, recognition, and points to motivate reading	8	73%
Parental guidance and monitoring	Supervision, reminders, and structured routines at home	9	82%
Time management and task organization	Students prioritizing and scheduling reading tasks	6	55%
Use of digital and print resources	Combination of books, tablets, and online materials	7	64%

Source: Interview Data

Table 8 presents the key strategies and interventions implemented by students, teachers, and parents to support reading development, as derived from the qualitative data. The most dominant strategy identified was teacher-led instructional strategies (91%).

Table 9. Themes on Perceived Effectiveness of the Reading Program

Theme	Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Improved reading comprehension	Better understanding of texts and vocabulary	9	82%
Increased reading engagement	More frequent reading and participation	8	73%
Structured reading behavior	Development of reading routines and habits	7	64%

Extrinsic motivation (compliance-based)	Reading driven by requirements and rewards	8	73%
Mixed experiences (difficulty and pressure)	Some students found texts difficult or tiring	5	45%

Source: Interview Data

Table 9 presents the perceptions of students, parents, and the teacher regarding the effectiveness of the Scholastic Literacy Pro program in improving reading comprehension. The most prominent finding was improved reading comprehension (82%).

Table 10. Themes on Contextual Factors Influencing Reading

Theme	Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Home environment support	Presence of books, routines, and parental encouragement	9	82%
Gadget exposure and digital distraction	High use of mobile devices affecting reading habits	10	91%
Parental involvement	Active guidance, monitoring, and intervention	8	73%
School environment and instructional support	Teacher strategies and classroom practices	7	64%
Competing responsibilities	Academic load and extracurricular activities	6	55%

Source: Interview Data

Table 10 presents the contextual factors that influenced students' reading performance and engagement, based on the qualitative analysis of student, parent, and teacher responses. The most dominant factor identified was gadget exposure and digital distraction (91%).

Table 11. Thematic Development from NVivo Analysis

Category	Main Themes	Subthemes	Emerging Themes
Contextual Factors	Reading Environment	Home Preference; School Distraction	Home vs School Gap
Contextual Factors	Motivation & Engagement	Intrinsic; Extrinsic; Compliance	Extrinsic Dominance
Challenges	Barriers	Gadgets; Workload; Difficulty	Digital Interference
Strategies, Interventions, and Reading Activities	Support Systems	Parental; Teacher; Strategies	Shared Responsibility
Program Effectiveness	Outcomes	Improved Comprehension; Engagement	Gradual Improvement

Source: NVivo-Thematic Analysis Output

Table 11 presents the hierarchical organization of qualitative findings. The categories are challenges, strategies, interventions and reading activities, program effectiveness, and contextual factors influencing students' reading comprehension. Main themes represent broad categories derived from the data. Subthemes reflect specific patterns

identified through coding. Emerging themes capture higher-level interpretations that explain relationships across categories. The progression demonstrates how raw qualitative data were synthesized into structured insights for analysis and discussion.

Table 12. Joint Display of Quantitative and Qualitative Integration

Quantitative Finding	Qualitative Evidence	Integrated Interpretation	Type of Integration
No significant difference in reading comprehension when grouped by sex (Table 5.1)	<i>Table 8 – Challenges</i> (Gadget distraction, vocabulary difficulty); <i>Table 9 – Strategies</i> (Teacher-led strategies, parental support)	Both male and female students experience similar challenges and receive comparable support, explaining the absence of performance differences	Convergent
Significant difference in reading comprehension when grouped by class section (Table 5.2)	<i>Table 11 – Contextual Factors</i> (School environment and instructional support); <i>Table 9 – Strategies</i> (Teacher-led instruction)	Differences in instructional context and classroom environment contribute to variations in performance between Science and Regular classes	Convergent
No significant difference when grouped by socio-economic status (Table 5.3)	<i>Table 11 – Contextual Factors</i> (Home environment support, parental involvement); <i>Table 9 – Strategies</i> (Parental guidance and monitoring)	Strong home support and parental involvement across groups may reduce the expected impact of socio-economic differences	Expansion
Significant improvement in reading comprehension over time (Table 6)	<i>Table 10 – Effectiveness</i> (Improved comprehension, increased engagement); <i>Table 9 – Strategies</i> (Teacher-led instruction, rewards)	The implementation of structured strategies and the reading program contributed to measurable improvement in comprehension	Convergent
High proportion of students in Below Basic level in pretest and posttest (Table 4)	<i>Table 8 – Challenges</i> (Vocabulary difficulty, low motivation, academic workload, gadget distraction)	Persistent barriers hinder students’ ability to move beyond lower proficiency levels despite overall gains	Convergent
Shift in performance levels (increase in Basic and Advanced; slight decrease in Proficient) (Table 4)	<i>Table 10 – Effectiveness</i> (Mixed experiences; extrinsic motivation); <i>Table 9 – Strategies</i> (Varied interventions)	Improvements are uneven due to differences in motivation, engagement, and response to interventions	Expansion
No significant SES effect (Table 5.3)	<i>Table 11 – Contextual Factors</i> (Gadget exposure and digital distraction – dominant); <i>Table 8 – Challenges</i> (Gadget distraction)	Digital distraction emerges as a stronger influencing factor than socio-economic status in shaping reading engagement	Expansion / Partial Divergence

Source: Research Data and Interview Data

Table 12 presents the integration of quantitative and qualitative findings through a joint display approach. The statistical results were aligned with relevant qualitative themes and evidence to determine areas of convergence, expansion, and partial divergence. The integrated findings provided a comprehensive view of students’

reading comprehension development by combining numerical trends with participants' experiences and perspectives.

Discussion

Reading Comprehension Performance and Growth Over Time

The findings revealed that most Grade 10 students initially demonstrated Below Basic reading comprehension levels, indicating persistent literacy challenges despite the school's implementation of reading support initiatives. This result is consistent with previous studies conducted at St. Paul University Surigao, where a substantial proportion of learners also performed below expected reading proficiency levels (Gortifacion, 2017; Oposa et al., 2025; Arbis et al., 2025). The prevalence of low initial reading performance suggests that reading comprehension remains a continuing concern requiring sustained instructional support and literacy interventions.

Despite the low baseline performance, students demonstrated significant improvements in their posttest Lexile scores. This finding suggests that reading development is a gradual process that can be enhanced through continuous exposure to reading activities, guided instruction, and structured literacy support. The result supports the findings of Kim et al. (2020) and Petscher et al. (2020), who emphasized that consistent engagement in reading instruction contributes to measurable gains in reading comprehension. The improvement observed in this study further supports the potential contribution of the Scholastic Literacy Pro program in facilitating reading growth among learners.

Influence of Student Profile Variables

The study found no significant differences in reading comprehension performance when students were grouped according to sex and socio-economic status. This finding suggests that reading comprehension development may not be determined solely by demographic characteristics but may instead be influenced by the quality of instructional support and learning experiences available to students. The qualitative findings further indicated that parental support, reading routines, and learner engagement may have helped minimize differences associated with socio-economic background.

In contrast, class section emerged as a significant factor influencing reading performance. Students from the Science class consistently obtained higher reading comprehension scores than the students from the Regular classes. This result aligns with the findings of Khorramdel et al. (2020), who reported that academic grouping and instructional context significantly affect reading achievement. Similarly, Maborang and Balero (2023) highlighted that differences in instructional quality, academic expectations, and learning environments contribute to variations in reading outcomes. The finding indicates that educational context plays an important role in shaping reading comprehension performance.

Challenges Affecting Reading Comprehension Development

The qualitative findings identified vocabulary limitations, low motivation, digital distractions, and academic workload as major challenges affecting students' reading comprehension development. Vocabulary difficulties restricted students' ability to understand unfamiliar words and comprehend complex texts, while low motivation reduced students' engagement in reading activities. Participants also highlighted the

influence of gadgets and social media, which often diverted attention away from reading and contributed to decreased reading habits.

These findings support the study of Elleman et al. (2009), who emphasized that limited vocabulary knowledge hinders students' ability to construct meaning from texts and negatively affects comprehension. Similarly, Delgado et al. (2018) noted that digital distractions and competing online activities may reduce sustained reading engagement, while Guthrie and Klauda (2014) highlighted that motivation plays a critical role in students' reading achievement and comprehension performance.

Strategies and Perceived Effectiveness of Scholastic Literacy Pro

Participants identified guided reading, teacher support, parental involvement, and structured reading routines as important strategies that contributed to reading development. These findings highlight the collaborative role of schools and families in supporting literacy growth. The qualitative data further revealed positive perceptions regarding the effectiveness of the Scholastic Literacy Pro program, particularly in helping students access appropriate reading materials, monitor their progress, and engage in reading activities aligned with their reading levels.

These findings are consistent with previous studies demonstrating the effectiveness of Scholastic Literacy Pro in promoting reading engagement and comprehension through personalized reading experiences and continuous progress monitoring (Scholastic Inc., 2015; Solis, 2024). The integration of assessment, monitoring, and instructional support within the program appears to provide a structured framework that supports reading development.

Contextual Factors Influencing Reading Development

The findings further revealed that reading comprehension is influenced by contextual factors beyond the classroom. Home reading environments, parental involvement, and socio-environmental conditions shaped students' reading experiences and engagement. While socio-economic status was not statistically significant, qualitative evidence showed that supportive home environments contributed positively to students' reading habits and motivation.

This finding demonstrated that reading comprehension is a multidimensional phenomenon influenced by both instructional and environmental factors. Consistent with socio-cultural perspectives of learning, students' literacy development is strengthened when meaningful support is provided across school and home settings.

Integration of Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The integration of quantitative and qualitative findings provided a more comprehensive understanding of students' reading comprehension development. Areas of *convergence* were observed in the significant improvement in reading comprehension performance and participants' reports of increased engagement and comprehension, while *expansion* occurred when qualitative findings explained non-significant results, particularly the role of parental support and home reading routines despite differences in socio-economic status. A *partial divergence* was also identified, as digital distractions and reading environments emerged as influential factors in the qualitative findings despite not being directly reflected in the quantitative results. Consistent with the explanatory sequential mixed-methods approach, the integration of both datasets enabled a deeper interpretation of students' reading comprehension development and the factors influencing their reading performance (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018). These findings demonstrate how qualitative evidence helped explain and

contextualize quantitative trends, thereby providing a more holistic understanding of students' reading comprehension development.

Implications, Limitations, and Directions for Future Research

The study contributes to the growing body of literacy research by providing a short-term longitudinal and mixed-methods examination of reading comprehension development among Grade 10 students using Scholastic Literacy Pro. By integrating quantitative Lexile data with qualitative perspectives from students, parents, and teachers, the study offers a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing reading growth.

However, the findings should be interpreted in light of several limitations. The study was conducted in a single institution and focused only on Grade 10 students. The short-term longitudinal design involved only two measurement points within one academic year, limiting conclusions regarding long-term reading development. Future studies may employ longer observation periods, larger samples, and additional variables to further examine reading comprehension growth and literacy program effectiveness.

Conclusion

This study examined the reading comprehension development of Grade 10 students using the Scholastic Literacy Pro program through a short-term longitudinal mixed-methods approach. The findings revealed that students demonstrated improvement in reading comprehension over time, although most initially belonged to the Below Basic proficiency level. Significant were observed according to class section, while sex and socio-economic status did not significantly influence reading performance. Qualitative findings further showed that reading development was shaped by vocabulary knowledge, reading motivation, digital distractions, instructional support, parental involvement, and reading routines.

The integration of quantitative and qualitative findings suggests that reading comprehension development is a gradual and multifaceted process influenced by both instructional and contextual factors. These findings highlight the value of combining assessment-based monitoring with home and school support systems in promoting literacy development. While the study was limited to one institution and a short-term observation period, it provides evidence that may inform literacy planning, instructional decision-making, and reading program implementation. Future studies may examine longer-term reading development and explore additional factors that influence students' reading comprehension outcomes.

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